

Fluorescence resonance energy transfer: A spectroscopic study

Dipti Singharoy*, Swadesh Ghosh and Subhash Chandra Bhattacharya*

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata-700 032, India

E-mail: diptisingharoy@gmail.com, sbjuchem@yahoo.com

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Fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) from trypsin to a probe molecule, sodium salt of anthracene-1,5-disulfonate (1,5-AS) has specifically been used to monitor the extent of protein denaturation in buffer media. The data obtained from steady state fluorescence spectral studies and time resolved measurement indicated that the FRET from tryptophan (Trp) residue of trypsin to 1,5-AS occurred effectively in buffer medium. The stability of the complex formed between albumins and the probe has been recognized from the conformational changes of proteins. Steady state and time resolved studies in association with circular dichroism study have experimentally established the FRET efficiency and protein denaturation.

Keywords: Protein, FRET, lifetime, circular dichroism.

Introduction

Trypsin protein consists of 223 amino acid residues with a molecular weight of 23,300 Da. The individual chains are held together by six disulfide bridges. It is composed of two domains of nearly equal size, the major constituent of each domain being a set of six anti-parallel strands of polypeptide chain tied together into a β -sheet unit by a network of H-bonds¹. It is the most abundant protease in nature and plays an essential role in digestion and deconstruction of food proteins and other physiological processes including hemostasis, apoptosis, signal transduction, reproduction and immune response². Proteins are frequently used in biophysical and biochemical studies and have many physiological functions, ability to bind different categories of small molecule, drug and other bioactive molecules because of the availability of hydrophobic pockets inside the protein network and the flexibility of the albumins in adapting their shapes^{3,4}.

For the study of dynamics of biological molecules, anthracene and its derivatives (here sodium salt of anthracene-1,5-disulfonate i.e. 1,5-AS) are used as fluorescent probes for its high fluorescence yield⁵. On sulfonation the bi-sulfonate formed become water-soluble and produces interesting fluorescence characteristics. The sulfonate group affects the overall symmetry of the anthracene moiety and also introduces negatively charged centre in the molecule. Because of their antiproliferative activities against a panel of tumor cell lines, including multi-drug-resistant phenotypes, an-

thracene and its derivatives have drawn renewed attention as new drug delivery technologies^{6,7}. The drug is widely used in chemiluminescence⁸, protein separation and refolding in the downstream processing of biotechnology⁹, metabolically competent human hepatoma cells for the detection of mutagens and antimutagens¹⁰.

Herein we have studied the spectral characteristics of 1,5-AS in buffer media with trypsin. A photo physical process i.e. fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) can monitor protein folding. Due to FRET simultaneously quenching of donor fluorescence and enhancement of acceptor fluorescence can take place¹¹. In particular, FRET has been widely investigated due to biological significance associated with the biomedical imaging. Herein, we report efficient FRET between trypsin and probe molecule (1,5-AS) in HEPES buffer medium. The aim of this work is to investigate the extent of conformational change of trypsin that occurs upon binding with probe in HEPES buffer. The feasibility of energy transfer in buffer media have also been determined. These would reveal details about the structural heterogeneity of proteins, and the structural fluctuations of these molecules over moderately large distances. The efficiency of energy transfer is limited only by the distance of closest possible approach between donor and acceptor. To confirm FRET study time resolved fluorescence spectra were taken and to investigate secondary structure of trypsin, circular dichroism (CD) was studied in buffer media.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

Materials:

1,5-AS (Scheme 1) was synthesized by reducing the corresponding anthraquinone with Zn dust and 20% NaOH solution for 4–6 h¹². The product was treated with active charcoal to remove traces of anthraquinone and other impurities and crystallized four times from water and obtained as a sodium salt. Trypsin from bovine (Sigma, >98%) and HEPES buffer (N-[2-hydroxyethyl]piperazine-N'-[2-ethanesulphonic acid]) were used as received. HEPES buffer (10 mM) were used throughout the study.

Scheme 1. Structure of 1,5-AS.

Methods:

Absorption spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu (model UV1700) UV-Vis spectrophotometer with a matched pair of silica cuvettes against a solvent blank reference in the wavelength range 200–700 nm. All corrected steady state fluorescence spectra were recorded in a 1 cm path length quartz cuvette at 298 K using a Shimadzu spectrofluorimeter (model RF 5301). All fluorescence spectra were corrected with respect to instrumental response. All measurements were done repeatedly and reproducible results were obtained. FRET experiments were carried out by keeping the concentrations of trypsin fixed at 2.4 μM throughout the experiment. A stock solution of concentration 5 mM 1,5-AS was prepared for the experiment. Whenever needed it was diluted in different case. An excitation wavelength of 280 nm was used in all cases for selective excitation of the Trp residue, and emission spectra were recorded from 290 to 500 nm. Fluorescence decay curves were obtained from time resolved intensity decay by the method of time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) using a nanosecond diode LED at 280 nm (IBH, nanoLED) as a light source. The data stored in a multichannel analyzer was routinely transferred to IBH DAS-

6 decay analysis software. For all the lifetime measurements, the fluorescence decay curves were analyzed by bi exponential iterative fitting program provided by IBH such as in eq. (1).

$$F(t) = \sum_i a_i e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where a_i is the pre exponential factor representing the fractional contribution to the time resolved decay of the component with lifetime τ_i . Average lifetime $\langle\tau\rangle$ for bi exponential decay can be calculated as in eq. (2).

$$\langle\tau\rangle = \frac{a_1\tau_1 + a_2\tau_2}{a_1 + a_2} \quad (2)$$

Circular dichroism (CD) was measured by a Jasco spectropolarimeter (J-815), equipped with a Jasco Peltier-type temperature controller using a rectangular quartz cuvette of path length 1 cm. The measurements were carried out at 298 K. Far UV-CD spectra were collected with a protein concentration of 0.18 μM with 1.0 cm path length in the range of 200–240 nm. For only CD measurement HEPES buffer of 1 mM was used.

Results and discussion

Emission behavior of 1,5-AS in presence of trypsin:

The emission spectra of 1,5-AS in presence of different concentrations of trypsin were recorded on excitations of the probe at 366 nm (λ_{exc}) in HEPES buffer (10.0 mM, pH 7) media. In absence of protein an emission band at 414 nm (λ_{em}^{max}) of 1,5-AS is obtained. On addition of trypsin, the emission profile of 1,5-AS shows decrease in the fluorescence intensity. The decrease of fluorescence intensity of 1,5-AS in presence of trypsin can be rationalized in terms of binding of the probe (1,5-AS) with trypsin. But the strength of the binding can be understood through the binding constant values between the probe and the protein. The binding constants between the probe and the protein have been determined from the fluorescence intensity data following the method described by Almgren *et al.*¹³ in eq. (3). According to this method

$$\frac{F_{\infty} - F_0}{F - F_0} = 1 + \frac{1}{K[\text{protein}]} \quad (3)$$

where F_0 , F and F_∞ are the fluorescence intensities of 1,5-AS in the absence of protein, in protein solution, and under conditions of complete saturation of binding between probe and protein, respectively. K represents the binding constant between the probe in the excited state and protein. The plot of $(F_\infty - F_0)/(F - F_0)$ vs $1/[\text{protein}]$ (eq. (3)) shows the linearity (Fig. 1) in buffer media. The binding constant values $7.4 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$ in buffer media are tabulated in Table 1. From binding constant values (Table 1) it is evident that 1,5-AS is strongly bind with BSA/HSA compared to trypsin in buffer media¹⁴.

Fig. 1. (a) Fluorescence spectra of 1,5-AS solution with increasing trypsin concentrations ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 366 \text{ nm}$) in HEPES buffer medium. (b) The plot of $(F_\infty - F_0)/(F - F_0)$ vs $[\text{protein}]^{-1}$.

Energy transfer from trypsin to 1,5-AS in different media:

The fluorescence spectra of trypsin have been recorded with different concentrations of 1,5-AS in HEPES buffer (10 mM, pH 7) media (Fig. 2). The emission spectra of trypsin in the absence of 1,5-AS shows an emission maximum at 333 nm, when excited at 280 nm. The fluorescence intensities of trypsin upon addition of 1,5-AS is decreased, whereas simultaneously fluorescence intensity at 414 nm of 1,5-AS increased and a clear isoemissive point was appeared at 381 nm in buffer. So it is clear that 1,5-AS binds to the proteins, indicating the possibility of an energy transfer process between the proteins and the probe. In this cases spiked nature of the protein's emission spectra at the saturation point of the titration by 1,5-AS indicate possibility of protein denaturation.

Considering the fact that 1,5-AS has reasonable absorption at a wavelength range where trypsin emits, the pair was judged as a good pair of donor-acceptor system for the FRET study. The fluorescence spectrum of the mixture of donor and acceptor did not show any additional new broad peak at longer wavelengths, which evidences the absence of exciplex

formation between the donor (photo excited) and the acceptor molecules. Thus, the decrease in the fluorescence intensity of the donor with an increasing acceptor concentration indicates a non-radiative energy transfer from the excited donor to the acceptor. Considering the conditions of FRET process and according to Förster's theory¹¹, the energy transfer efficiency (E) is related to the distance between acceptor and donor (r_0) also to the critical energy transfer distance when the efficiency of transfer is 50%; (R_0)¹⁵ as given in the eq. (4).

$$E = 1 - \frac{F}{F_0} = \frac{R_0^6}{R_0^6 + r_0^6} \quad (4)$$

where F and F_0 denote the steady-state fluorescence intensities of proteins in presence and absence of probe. R_0 value can be calculated according to eq. (5)¹¹.

$$R_0^6 = 8.79 \times 10^{-25} \times \chi^2 \times n^4 \times \chi \Phi \times J \quad (5)$$

where χ^2 is the orientation factor related to the geometry of the donor and acceptor of dipoles and χ^2 is generally assumed equal to be $2/3$ which is the value for donors and acceptors which randomize by rotational diffusion prior to energy transfer; n is the average refractive index of medium in the wavelength range where spectral overlap is significant; Φ is the fluorescence quantum yield of the donor; J is the spectral overlap integral between the emission spectrum of the donor and the absorption spectrum of the acceptor (Fig. 2), which can be calculated by eq. (6)¹¹.

$$J = \frac{\int_0^\infty F(\lambda) \varepsilon(\lambda) \lambda^4 d\lambda}{\int_0^\infty F(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (6)$$

where $F(\lambda)$ is the corrected fluorescence intensity of the donor in the wavelength range from λ to $\lambda + d\lambda$; $\varepsilon(\lambda)$ is the extinction coefficient of the acceptor at λ .

From the overlapping of the absorption spectra of the acceptor and the emission spectra of the donor, J can be calculated by integrating the spectra for $\lambda = 290\text{--}400 \text{ nm}$ using $\chi^2 = 2/3$, $n = 1.38$, and $\Phi = 0.15$ ¹⁶. In buffer, using eqs. (4)–(6) the values of J , R_0 , E and r_0 have been calculated and the values are summarized in Table 1. The average distances between a donor fluorophore and acceptor

Fig. 2. (a) Fluorescence resonance energy transfer profile from trypsin to 1,5-AS in buffer medium and (b) the overlap of the normalized fluorescence spectra of donor trypsin and the relative absorption spectra of acceptor 1,5-AS in HEPES buffer media.

fluorophore are on the range $0.5R_0 < r_0 < 1.5R_0$, which indicate that the energy transfer from protein to 1,5-AS occurs.

The occurrence of FRET with trypsin suggests that the probe 1,5-AS resides close to the Trp moieties of the proteins in buffer media. The values of energy transfer efficiency from trypsin to 1,5-AS in buffer is 33% which is low compared to BSA/HSA:1,5-AS pairs¹⁴. As a result donor acceptor distance of trypsin:1,5-AS pair increases and energy transfer efficiency decreases than BSA/HSA:1,5-AS pairs¹⁷.

Fluorescence quenching:

The quenching of the fluorescence of the donor (tryptophan residue of trypsin) with the addition of acceptor (1,5-AS) in buffer media was followed by Stern-Volmer relation¹¹ in eq. (7).

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{SV} [Q] \quad (7)$$

where F_0 , F are fluorescence intensities of donor in the absence and in the presence of acceptor molecule respectively, K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer constant and $[Q]$ is the quencher (here acceptor) concentration¹¹. A straight line in the Stern-Volmer plot (Fig. 3) is obtained in the concentration range of the acceptor studied in buffer medium.

In buffer media the linearity of the plot indicates that only one type of quenching occurs in the systems¹⁸. The K_{SV}

values are given in Table 1. From the absence of any additional absorption band in the donor-acceptor mixture, the possibility of ground state complex formation is ruled out and the quenching is rationalized in terms of energy transfer. Since there is good overlap region between the fluorescence spectra of proteins and absorption spectra of the quencher, the FRET occurs during the quenching process. In tune with these studies, this observation suggests that the dominant mechanism of fluorescence quenching is the resonance energy transfer through long-range dipole-dipole interaction rather than the simple diffusion limited process between the excited donor and the ground state acceptor molecule. The binding affinity, Stern-Volmer constant and binding constant values agree well with each other.

Time-resolved fluorescence measurements:

Fluorescence lifetime shows a sensitive indicator of local environment in which a given fluorophore is placed, also it is rich in information and provide unique insights into the system under investigation¹⁹. Time resolved studies throw further light on the nature of excited state interaction between the probe and protein²⁰. In order to deduce an elaborate analysis of FRET study, the fluorescence life time of trypsin ($\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm) in aqueous buffer medium has been measured (Fig. 3). Due to gradual addition upto 6.0 mM amount of an acceptor probe solution, the lifetime of the donor decreases in buffer media. The decrease in lifetime is due to increase in non-radiative decay channels and energy trans-

Fig. 3. (a) Plot of F_0/F vs [1,5-AS] in buffer media for trypsin and (b) fluorescence decay curves associated with lamp profile for trypsin in buffer medium with variation of [1,5-AS].

Table 1. Binding constants (K), various energy transfer parameters and Stern-Volmer constants (K_{SV}) in buffer from donor to acceptor (1,5-AS)

	K ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$)	E (%)	r (Å)	R_0 (Å)	J ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^3$)	K_{SV} ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$)
Tps : 1,5-AS	7.5×10^3	33.0	68.5	61.0	2.1×10^{-12}	8.5×10^3

Table 2. Fluorescence lifetime of trypsin in buffer media as a function of concentration of 1,5-AS

[1,5-AS] (mM)	τ_1 (ns)	τ_2 (ns)	a_1	a_2	τ_{avg} (ns)	χ^2
0.0	2.5	3.7	0.7	0.3	2.9	1.01
6.0	1.9	4.1	0.9	0.1	2.2	1.01

fer from donor to acceptor¹¹. In all cases, the fluorescence decay curves are fitted to bi exponential function with acceptable values for χ^2 (Table 2). The origin of this bi exponential decay is not very clear¹, but in analogy to other such studies, there are several reasons; different components may arise due to binding of the probe to different binding sites of the protein, ground state heterogeneity, time-dependent relaxation around the excited state or the intrinsic heterogeneity of Trp fluorescence^{21,22}. The average lifetime (τ_{avg}) of Trp residue of trypsin in buffer media decreases from 2.9 to 2.2 ns with the addition of 1,5-AS (Table 2). From Table 2 it is seen that in buffer media the distribution parameter a_1 increases and a_2 decreases. Also we see that longer lived component (τ_2) have the small distribution parameter (a_2) and shorter-lived component (τ_1) have maximum distribution parameter (a_1) to the time-resolved decay for all the environments. However the average life times of trypsin have been considered in order to gain a qualitative picture. Donor residue (Trp) may face different environments or there may be present two components.

Structural stability of trypsin:

Far-UV circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy indicates the alteration induced in the secondary structure of trypsin due to unfolding of protein. As reported by Bharmoria *et al.*²³ that change in the fluorescence intensity cannot solely be considered as a proof of unfolding of protein, complementary changes in the secondary structure of protein can validate the fluorescence results. The CD spectra of trypsin at different concentration of 1,5-AS in buffer medium (1 mM of pH 7.0) have been shown in Fig. 4. The CD spectra of trypsin upto 0.18 μ M concentration of 1,5-AS have been observed. Trypsin shows two characteristic negative peaks at 208 and 222 nm due to α -helix structure. In buffer media, secondary structure of trypsin denatured due to addition of 1,5-AS. After the addition of 1,5-AS, the CD spectra of trypsin are fully denatured in experimental environment, indicating that the binding of 1,5-AS can change the secondary structure of protein, especially α -helix structure.

Fig. 4. CD spectra of trypsin with addition of [1,5-AS].

Before titration with 1,5-AS in buffer medium the ellipticity of trypsin is 64.6% and after completion of 1,5-AS addition the ellipticity of trypsin attain a value of 56.0% at 0.18 μ M of 1,5-AS. So in buffer media, loss of helicity of trypsin is 8.6% due to addition of 1,5-AS. This has confirmed that 1,5-AS has damaged the protein structure which has also been observed from emission spectra. Thus we conclude that 1,5-AS disrupts α -helical network and lead to a more solvent exposed protein structure.

Conclusions

The results described herein provides insights into the photophysical properties of a fluorescent probe 1,5-AS in the presence of trypsin in buffer media. We have demonstrated enhancement of the sensitized acceptor emission from one binding event by utilizing a potentially bioactive compound 1,5-AS along with trypsin as energy donor. The binding constants of the protein with the probe have been estimated and the high order of values implies fluorescence resonance energy transfer from the donor to the acceptor. Steady state emission studies and related calculations reveal that the probe protein binding is occurred. Energy efficacy, Förster radii and overlap integral values indicate the occurrence of an efficient FRET process between the donor trypsin and the acceptor 1,5-AS molecules. Far-UV circular dichroism study establish that there is a change of the structural stability of trypsin upon binding with probe 1,5-AS in buffer media. These all experimental and theoretical results endorse 1,5-AS as promising FRET pair with trypsin in buffer media.

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